

Post-print version:

NON-CENTRALIZED HIERARCHICAL MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL STRATEGY OF FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND FARMS FOR FATIGUE LOAD REDUCTION

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This work has been published in **Renewable Energy**:

H.D.P Gonzalez and J.L. Domínguez-García, “Non-centralized Hierarchical Model Predictive Control Strategy of Floating Offshore Wind Farms for Fatigue Load Reduction”, *Renewable Energy*, vol. 187, pp. 248-256, 2022.

Final version available at:

URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148122000568>

DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2022.01.046

BibTex:

```
@Article{gonzalez2022non,  
  Title = {Non-centralized Hierarchical Model Predictive Control Strategy of  
    Floating Offshore Wind Farms for Fatigue Load Reduction},  
  Author = {Hector Del Pozo Gonzalez and Jose Luis Domínguez-García},  
  Journal = {Renewable Energy},  
  Year = {2022},  
  Number = {},  
  Pages = {248-256},  
  Volume = {187},  
  Doi = {10.1016/j.renene.2022.01.046}  
}
```

Non-centralized hierarchical model predictive control strategy of floating offshore wind farms for fatigue load reduction

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Offshore wind farms,
Floating Wind Turbines
Fatigue Loads
Predictive Control
Wake Effect
Cluster
Hierarchical control

ABSTRACT

Wind power is increasing rapidly and specially offshore wind. Offshore wind offers certain advantages as more constant wind and additional space without large restriction. However, deep-waters require floating technologies. A key drawback of offshore wind is the reduced windows for operation and maintenance. Therefore, the use of optimal control algorithms that ensure the correct operation of the wind farm is essential. Offshore wind farms are usually oriented towards a defined direction of wind flow, so upstream turbines tend to provide more active power, carrying higher fatigue load, which results in uneven distribution of fatigue across the wind farms. Loads must be distributed among the members of the farm, to extend the farm and turbines life and reduce possible maintenance or breakage costs. Taking into account wake effects as well as hydrodynamic impacts which add additional motion and stress to the system, this paper presents a wind farm Model Predictive Controller (MPC) in order to optimize the loads of each wind turbine for life-extension. The results of the control show how the power generation is met and the load distribution are better balanced reducing system stress.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, offshore wind turbines are one of the most important renewable energy sources and the offshore wind industry is growing rapidly. This growth also influences wind farms dimension, since current wind farms consist of a large amount of wind turbines (WT) in order to reduce costs and meet grid requirements. Having a large number of participating turbines also increases the amount of sensors and data, so the development of more sophisticated, fast and efficient control algorithms is essential to ensure proper behavior of the wind farm (WF).

In recent years research related to the optimal control of wind farms has increased, seeking different objectives, such as maximize the extracted power, minimize the power losses caused by the wake effect or provide services to the grid, among others [1, 2, 3]. In [4], a good review of different approach control strategies developed for wind farms in recent times is presented.

Active control for reduction of fatigue loads has been one of the objectives sought. The point of interest is to minimize fatigue loads simultaneously with controlling power. Nowadays, there are wind farms in which the turbines work individually, at the maximum power set-point imposed, regardless any farm data. In this case, and in control strategies that seek to distribute the power set-points according to the turbine's output capacity in prevailing wind conditions, it must be taken into account the wake effect. The reason is because the wind speed of the downstream turbines decreases when the upstream turbines acquire wind energy in a wind farm, which means that the downstream turbines will have less allocated production. Furthermore, this will lead to lower degree of fatigue compared to upstream turbines.

After long operating times, the fatigue value of the units located on the edge of the wind farm will be higher, resulting in an uneven distribution of fatigue. This will lead to more continuous maintenance or even the possibility of turbine breakage.

The structural loads acting on offshore wind turbines (OWTs), can be classified as dynamic loads or static loads. Static loads are mainly related to the weight of the elements of the structure, while dynamics are related to the structure interaction with air and water, being aerodynamic and hydrodynamic interactions, respectively. As defined in [5], the main challenges are related to dynamic loads.

Different proposals to solve this problem have been published in recent times. Authors in [6] present a hierarchical control, in which the high-level control distributes power and loads, while the lower level reacts to sudden disturbances. Wake effect is not considered in this work, and a combination of on-line and off-line solutions is used to solve the problem. A similar solution is proposed in [7], where another hierarchical control structure is presented, with a consensus based upper-level and a MPC based lower level. Consensus control ensures power dispatch while the decentralized MPC ensures power tracking and minimum variation in shaft torque and thrust force. Rivero presents in [8] deterministic and stochastic MPC algorithms for dispatching the power command and reducing the mechanical loads. Since a wind flow model is not used in this work, the author predicts the interfaced WT wind velocity using an ARMA process. Kazda et al. exposes in [9] a strategy based on MPC which ensures power tracking and reduces fatigue, represented by a damage equivalent loads (DEL) look-up table. The author's proposal demonstrates a greater fatigue reduction than a classic PI control. A supervisory control is presented in [10], dispatching power references to WTs while operating close to their maximum power curve, obtaining shaft fatigue reduction. A wake model is not included in this proposal.

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Some of the previous articles get a reduction in fatigue with centralized strategies but, as mentioned before, current wind farms consist of a large amount of WT in order to reduce costs and meet grid requirements. Having a greater number of WTs means increasing the amount of data received by the sensors and the orders to be sent by the controllers. For this reason, a centralized control strategy, which requires expensive communication networks, high computation tasks and causes a decrease in resilience [11], does not seem to be the best option to implement in large wind farms.

A solution to this problem can be dividing the wind farm into subsystems (clusters), formed by a smaller number of WT. The controllers of each subsystem will be treated as independent units, in which their elements will only be able to share information with each other, and not with elements of other subsystems. The correct operation of the complete system, is supervised by a non-centralized control. Therefore, with this strategy, communication links and computational costs can be reduced, due to cluster-level controllers only manage the internal operation and the state communication to a central unit controller.

In recent times, clustering techniques has been applied in wind farms to carry out non-centralized controls, focused on different purposes. For example, in [12], authors propose a wake-based partitioning approach to satisfy the power demanded by the grid operator while obtaining a reduction of computational costs. In [13], a clustering-based distributed optimization is implemented to improve yaw misalignment issues of WTs and the total power production. The present paper proposes a hierarchical non-centralized model predictive control (MPC) to ensure the correct power and fatigue loads distribution in a WF. The partitioning of the large-scale wind farm based on wake effect for computation costs reduction, is adopted from [12].

2. Fatigue status and sources of loading

Offshore wind turbines are subject to aerodynamic and hydrodynamic loads that vary over time, which means that the response to stress will also vary continuously, which can cause fatigue. Fatigue is the process that causes damage to structural components when they are subjected to stresses that change periodically. Due to these stress changes, the material will slowly deteriorate, which can cause the formation of cracks that will eventually lead to material breaking.

Wind turbines are subjected to variable fatigue loads during their useful life. Studies as [14] have shown that industrial turbines can be subjected to more than 10^8 load cycles. One possible classification of the type of loads, can be as continuous and unusual. Continuous can be the aerodynamic loads as forces and moments originating at the rotor and routed through the drive train and bed-plate, the drag loads from direct action of the wind on the tower, hydrodynamic loads on the submerged portion (wave, current, ice loads) or loads from actuation of operation and control devices (yaw, pitch, brake, torque control mechanisms) among others. On

Figure 1: Forces and moments in a spar WT

the other hand, unusual loads, would represent the loads derived from installation methods and maintenance actions [15].

Since this paper is focused on the minimization of the loads of the turbines with a control strategy, only the loads that cause fatigue are considered. Also, the analysis of the materials will not be carried out. Hence, the control variables will be directly the moments that originate the fatigue. Several authors as [6, 9, 16, 17, 18], define that the thrust force and shaft torque are the main forces that cause WT fatigue, due to affect the structure of the wind turbine tower and gearbox, respectively. The oscillatory transient of thrust force causes unwanted movement of the tower and leads to wind turbine fatigue. On the other hand, the shaft torque is transferred through the gearbox, which can lead to its failure, and even to its breakage. Other loads as variations in the flap-wise blade loading as depicted in figure 1 or the actuator wear and tear can be also considered to be more specific, but in this article we will only deal with the largest ones, the tower-base bending moment (M_{tb}) and the shaft moment (M_s). Therefore, a variable representing the fatigue state is declared as $S_F(M_{tb}, M_s)$, based on the moments originated by the mentioned forces. A detailed analysis of each load, is given in next subsections.

2.1. Tower base bending moments

The tower is of great importance in floating turbines, since can experience large bending moments, usually at the base. These moments are directly related to WT size, due to, a bigger distance between the hub (where the thrust force acts) and the base of the tower, lead to a larger moment.

Thrust force is the main responsible for the distribution of the bending moment along the tower [15].

In addition to the size of the turbine, the depth of the water must be considered, being the factors that establish whether hydrodynamics have an important role. In shallow water, aerodynamic loads predominate on the tower. However, as the water depths increase, the hydrodynamic loads progressively gain importance. Therefore, the aerodynamic and hydrodynamic forces that affect the tower must be defined. The aerodynamic force F_a , can be expressed as:

$$F_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^2 C_T(\lambda, \beta) \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the air density, A is the rotor disc area, v is the effective wind speed on the rotor and C_T represent the thrust coefficient, which depends on pitch angle β and λ , the ratio of the tip speed of the turbine blades to wind speed given by:

$$\lambda = \frac{R\omega_R}{v} \quad (2)$$

being ω_R is the angular velocity of the rotor and R the rotor radius.

From the hydrodynamic point of view, ocean wave and current interactions among the type of submerged or floating tower base structure, are analyzed. For slender structures, such as spar, Morison's formula is generally applied to determine the hydrodynamic loads, while in larger structures such as semi-submersible, due to the kinematic modification of the waves, an analysis of the wave diffraction effects must be performed, to determine the total loads. Also, when the structure is moving, for example in the case of floating structures, the radiation forces of the waves can be important and should be included.

Author in [19], based on the wave height, the structure diameter and the wave length shows the relative importance of drag, inertia and diffraction wave forces. It can be concluded that the spar type will be dominated by inertial forces, semi-submersible platform by diffraction, and jacket platform by drag events. In this work, a spar base structure is used, so it is assumed that the structure does not have a significant effect on the waves, and the hydrodynamic loading on the support structure can be computed via the Morison's equation, expressed as:

$$dF_h = \rho_w \frac{\pi}{4} D^2 (C_M \dot{v}_r + \dot{v}_w) dz + \rho_w \frac{\pi}{2} D^2 C_D v_r |v_r| dz \quad (3)$$

where dz represent the horizontal force on a vertical element of a cylinder (at level z), ρ_w is the sea water density, D is the tower outer diameter and C_D and C_M are the drag coefficient and the added mass coefficient, respectively. The variables v_r and \dot{v}_r represent the relative velocity and acceleration between body (v_b) and undisturbed water particles (v_w) [20]. By integrating throughout the length of submerged structure respect to the mean water level, the resulting force and moment are obtained. The positive sign force is assumed on the wave propagation direction.

2.2. Rotor shaft moments

This moment reflects the loads due to the inertia of the rotor and the aerodynamic loads, as a measure of the loads measured in the drive-train, being the predominant one. In addition, authors such as [21] demonstrate that the main shaft loads, including bending moments, are higher for FOWT than for land-based WT or fixed bottom WT. Therefore, this moment becomes a variable to take part in the control strategy.

Based on equation (1), the mechanical power captured by each wind turbine can be expressed as a static nonlinear mapping of the blade pitch angle and tip speed ratio as:

$$P_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta) \quad (4)$$

where P_a is the aerodynamic power captured by the WT. The wind power coefficient C_p reflects the wind energy capture capability of the wind turbine. The shaft bending moment is related to the torque exerted on the low-speed rotor shaft, whose equation is:

$$T_s = \frac{P_a}{\omega_R} \quad (5)$$

Therefore, by operating equations (4) and (5), the shaft bending moment can be expressed in terms of mechanical power as:

$$M_s = n_g \frac{P_a}{\omega_R} \quad (6)$$

where $n_g \in \mathbb{R}$ is the gearbox ratio of the wind generator.

3. Wake Effect in Offshore Wind Farms

In offshore wind farms, the wind speed that interfaces each downstream turbine in a wind farm is characterized by changes in the wind flow, an alteration that is defined as the turbine wake effect. This wake is characterized by a reduction in wind speed as a consequence of the extraction of energy, an increase in the intensity of turbulence due to the rotating effect of the turbine blade on the the wind, and an expanding wake described by the law of mass conservation [22]. There are other effects, such as wake deflection and wake recovery, but in the developed model are not considered.

In terms of power, equation (4) describe how the kinetic energy in the wind flow field is harvested by the rotor turbine and transformed into mechanical power. Therefore, based on wind speed, the available and generated power of each turbine are calculated. The wake effect, the position of the i^{th} turbine and the power references of the other wind turbines will influence the wind speed of each turbine v_i and, therefore, its available power, leading to substantial power losses.

Although there are different wake effect models, most are based on the Jensen/Park model [23], which propose a linear expansion of the wake considering the balance of momentum and the wind speed deficit evaluated by the turbine thrust

Figure 2: A detailed example of wind turbine wake effect shadowing

coefficient. This model was improved by [24], considering the characteristics of the wind turbine and calculating the wake losses with the sum of the squares of the speed deficits. In this paper, Park model is used to simulate the wind across the wind farm, where the wind speed deficit is calculated as a function of the distance among the turbines, the wind speed direction and the number of wakes affecting the downstream turbines. A complete description can be found in [25]. Since a large wind farm is analyzed, multiple wakes effects and partial shadowing are assumed. Therefore, considering that, due to the superposition, total wake effect is the sum of single wake effects, the wind interfaced by the i^{th} OWT, will be modeled as:

$$v_i = v_n \left(1 - \sum_{j \in N_i} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T} \right) \left(\frac{R}{s_k} \right)^2 \frac{A_{S,i}}{A_{0,i}} \right) \quad (7)$$

where v_n is the free-stream wind speed, $x_{i,j}$ the distance in the x-direction between turbines T_j and T_i , $s_k = r_{i,j}(x_{i,j})$ the radius of the wake generated by turbine T_j , and N_i , the set of indexes corresponding to the turbines upstream of T_i . $A_{0,i}$ and $A_{S,i}$ correspond to the rotor area and the shadowed area due to the upstream turbine, respectively.

Based on the scheme shown in figure 2, and assuming that all the turbines in the farm have the same diameter $2R$, by using trigonometric relationships, the shadowed area can be computed as:

$$A_{S,i} = s_k^2 \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{L_{i,j}}{s_k} \right) + R^2 \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{d_{i,j} - L_{i,j}}{s_k} \right) + d_{i,j} z_{i,j} \quad (8)$$

where $d_{i,j}$ is the distance between the centers of downstream turbine and the center of the wake effect, $L_{i,j}$ the distance

Figure 3: Waked wind farm layout, considering turbines oriented to the free-stream wind speed direction

between the centres of the wake area and $z_{i,j}$ is the vertical distance between the intersection points $A_{0,i}$ and $A_{S,i}$:

$$z_{i,j} = \frac{1}{d_{i,j}} \sqrt{4 \left(d_{i,j}^2 \right) \left(s_k^2 \right) - \left(d_{i,j}^2 + s_k^2 - R^2 \right)} \quad (9)$$

In figure 3, the effect of area overlapping in a wind farm formed by 36 turbines with a spacing between turbines of five rotor diameters, is presented.

By analyzing the layout and figure 2, result easy to note that when a change in the wind's flow interfaced by the i^{th} upstream turbine occurs, due to the distance $x_{i,j}$ between the turbines, the effect on the j^{th} downstream turbine is not detected until after a certain time, defined as wake delay $\tau_{i,j}$, calculated as:

$$\tau_{i,j} = \frac{x_{i,j}}{\Delta v_{i,j}} \quad (10)$$

where $x_{i,j}$ is the distance between turbines, and $\Delta v_{i,j}$ the speed increase between the i^{th} upstream turbine at time $t = 0$ and the j^{th} downstream wind turbine at time $t = \tau_{i,j}$.

In the wind farm analysis results, $\tau_{i,j}$ will be observed when control modifies the WTs power set-points, which leads to a wake effect reconfiguration and therefore to new values of available wind for each turbine.

4. Control Strategy

Model predictive control (MPC) has become very attractive by experts from different disciplines due to the possibility of predicting the future behavior of a system in a given time window. Based on future predictions and real-time system measurements or estimations, optimal control inputs are calculated with respect to a defined control target and subject to system constraints. The process is repeated cyclically, with a displaced horizon [26]. In this article, a MPC strategy is designed to achieve the desired goal.

Figure 4: Control Scheme

A control strategy that seeks to minimize the total load of the entire wind farm would be very difficult to achieve without altering the power deliver. Due to large difference between turbine loads are caused by wake effect, forcing all the turbines to have the same amount of loads for a long time, would not be efficient. Moreover, this could lead to unwanted malfunctions, maintenance requirements or reducing operating life of the wind farm turbines. In this article a distribution of the loads among the members of the wind farm is applied. The main objective of the developed controller must be follow the wind farm power reference while distributing the power in the wind farm such as every turbine suffers the same amount of the loads.

Figure 4 depicts the structure of the controller used. Taking $j = (j_1, \dots, j_m)$ as the cluster index, and $i = (i_1, \dots, i_n)$ as the number of wind turbines in each cluster, the N^{th} wind turbine can be denoted as $N_{j,i} = (N_{j,1}, \dots, N_{j,n})$, and its specific fatigue status as $S_F^{N_{j,i}}(M_{tb}, M_s)$.

The upper-level control (CUC), receives the information from each cluster controller, with the power generated by each one, since its only purpose is to ensure that the power delivered by the wind farm P_g^{WF} , is the same as the power required by the grid P_{dem}^{grid} . Note that the available power of a wind farm P_{av}^{WF} , is the sum of maximum available power of all WTs inside the wind farm.

Meanwhile, the cluster-level controllers (CLCs) receive from the N^{th} wind turbine, data of the available power $P_{av}^{N_{j,i}}$, data of the currently generating power $P_g^{N_{j,i}}$ and data of the fatigue status, in order to distribute the required power set-points $P_r^{N_{j,i}}$, in the most optimal way. Therefore, the turbines with the worst fatigue status S_F , will decrease their set-points, as long as the CUC power set-points allow it. At lower level, the internal control ensures that the power generated by each turbine is equal to the power demanded.

4.1. Cluster-level controllers (CLCs)

The CLCs aim to distribute the required power P_r^N set-points taking care on the turbines fatigue status, while

trying to minimize the power delivery tracking error. In this paper, based on state-space difference equations, the discrete approximated dynamic model is declared as:

$$\mathbf{x}(k+1) = A_d \mathbf{x}(k) + B_d \mathbf{u}(k) \quad (11)$$

being the matrix parameters (A_d, B_d) are the discretized version from the A, B system, where $A = -\tau \mathbf{I}^{N_j \times N_j}$ and $B = \tau \mathbf{I}^{N_j \times N_j}$, τ is a time constant that depends on the amount of cluster turbines.

Setting the initial time as k and the prediction horizon as N_p , the predictive model can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{X}(k) = F_a \mathbf{x}(k) + G_a \mathbf{U}(k) \quad (12)$$

being:

$$\mathbf{X}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} x(k+1) \\ \vdots \\ x(k+N_p) \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{U}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} u(k) \\ \vdots \\ u(k+N_p-1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$F_a = \begin{bmatrix} A_d \\ \vdots \\ A_d^{N_p} \end{bmatrix}; G_a = \begin{bmatrix} B_d & 0 & \dots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_d^{N_p-1} B_d & \dots & B_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

The chosen cluster MPC strategy is based on the optimization problem defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{u_c(k)} \quad & \sum_{k=1}^{N_p} \lambda_d J_d(x_c(k), u_c(k)) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & u_c^{min} \leq u_c(k) \leq u_c^{max} \\ & S_F^{N_{j,i}}(k) \leq S_F^{max}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

being $\lambda_d = (\lambda_{d,1}, \lambda_{d,2}, \lambda_{d,3})$ the weighing coefficients. S_F^{max} represents the maximum load values (i.e. fatigue) that a turbine can withstand during its life. This parameter can be designed by the manufacturer to protect the turbine from possible structural damage. Note that studies as [14] have shown that industrial turbines can be subjected to more than 10^8 load cycles.

The cost function presented in (16) enclose three objectives. The first and main one is to reduce power reference tracking error, imposed by the central control unit. In this way, the supervision of the correct quantity of power delivered by each cluster is ensured.

$$J_{d,1} = \left\| P_r^j - \sum_{i=1}^n P_g^{N_{j,i}} \right\|_{\lambda_{d,1}}^2$$

The second one is to penalize the turbines with a higher accumulated fatigue ratio in order to be able to dispatch,

whenever possible, a greater amount of power to the rest of the turbines.

$$J_{d,2} = \left\| 1 - \left(S_F^{N_{j,i}}(k) - \frac{1}{i} \sum_{i=1}^n S_F^{N_{j,i}} \right)^\xi u_c(k) \right\|_{\lambda_{d,2}}^2$$

The cost function depends on ξ , which determines the relative importance of the fatigue load distribution with respect to power tracking. When the available power of each cluster P_{av}^j is enough to satisfy the demand P_r^j , this term is not important ($\xi = 1$), allowing the references to be distributed considering fatigue status. On the contrary, when the reference powers of each cluster are close to the available power values (e.g. above 0.9 p.u.), the term provides a penalty to the cost function ($\xi = 0$), since it could prevent the controller from power tracking.

The last objective is imposed due to the need to protect the turbine from possible damage originating from the controller. Although the turbine has its own low-level control, which contains minimum and maximum operating limits, large variations in the CLC control signal would lead to sudden changes in the operation and set-points of the turbine, which throughout the time, could damage the turbine. Therefore, the operation of each turbine can be improved by imposing:

$$J_{d,3} = \|\Delta u_c(k)\|_{\lambda_{d,3}}^2$$

4.2. Central Unit Controller (CUC)

Higher level control ensures wind farm power delivery to the grid, $P_g^{WF} = P_{dem}^{grid}$. By receiving from the j^{th} CLC, the generated P_g^j and available P_{av}^j powers, the control sets an optimal distribution of new power references P_r^j in order to satisfy the demand. Here, the optimization problem is:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{u_p(k)} \quad & \sum_{k=1}^{N_p} \delta_\beta J_\beta(x_p(k), \Delta u_p(k)) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & u_p^{min} \leq u_p(k) \leq u_p^{max} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

with $\delta_\beta = (\delta_{\beta,1}, \delta_{\beta,2})$ as weighing coefficients. Similar as for the CLCs, the discrete approximated dynamic model of the entire wind farm can be modeled as:

$$\mathbf{x}(k+1) = A_d \mathbf{x}(k) + B_d \mathbf{u}(k) + E_d P_{dem}^{grid} \quad (18)$$

where:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -\tau_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & -\tau_i & 0 \\ -1 & \dots & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & \tau_i \\ 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$E_d = [0 \quad 0 \quad \dots \quad 1]^T \quad (21)$$

The control matrix u_p , is formed by the reference powers delivered to each cluster, $u_p = (P_r^{j,1}, \dots, P_r^{j,m})$ and the states matrix $x_p = [\Delta P_g^j, \epsilon_p]^T$, is formed by the increment of generated power of each cluster:

$$\Delta P_g^j = -\tau (P_g^j - P_r^j) \quad (22)$$

and the tracking demanded power error:

$$\epsilon_p = |P_{dem}^{grid} - P_g^{WF}| \quad (23)$$

In this equation, the power delivered by the wind farm P_g^{WF} , is the sum of the power delivered by each cluster:

$$P_g^{WF} = \sum_{j=1}^m P_g^j \quad (24)$$

The cost function (17) enclose two objectives. The main one is to ensure the power tracking, by minimizing the error (23):

$$J_{\beta,1} = \|x_p(k)\|_{\delta_{\beta,1}}^2$$

and the second one is:

$$J_{\beta,2} = \|\Delta u_p(k)\|_{\delta_{\beta,2}}^2$$

in order to minimize possible abrupt variations of the control signal, achieving a better performance.

5. Case Study

5.1. Setup

The following control strategies were tested for a wind farm of 180 MW rated power with 36 NREL-5MW offshore wind turbines [27]. The space between turbines is five rotor diameters (630 m) and are placed as shown in figure 3. The type of turbine chosen is shown in figure 1, which is a representation of the OC3-Hywind spar-type floating wind turbine model [28], whose main properties are shown in Table 1 and design parameters in Table 2.

The wind field and wake effect have been simulated using SimWindFarm [29], a MATLAB/Simulink toolbox for wind farm simulation and control. The MPC controllers were implemented with YALMIP [30] and GUROBI. In this work, based on data extracted during a period of 10 years in the Canary Islands, parameters of the most common average situations in that location are used, being 200m depth, 11m/s wind speed and taking airy wave theory, $T = 6.5s$ and $H = 1.5m$.

5.2. Results and analysis

In this section, the results of the analysed control strategies are presented. First, a strategy based on maximizing the generated and available power, and later, the strategy based

Table 1
Offshore wind turbine properties

Item	Value	Units
Rated Power	5	MW
Rotor diameter	126	m
Number of blades	3	
Blade length	61.5	m
Rated wind speed	11.4	m/s
Cut-in, cut-out wind speed	3, 25	m/s
Hub height above SWL	90	m
Tower base above SWL	10	m
Structure below SWL	120	m

Table 2
Floating wind turbine design parameters.

Item	Value	Units
Spar Diameter	9.4	m
Rotor Mass	$110 \cdot 10^3$	kg
Nacelle Mass	$240 \cdot 10^3$	kg
Floater Mass	$7.46 \cdot 10^6$	kg
Number of mooring lines	3	
Mooring lines angle	120	°

on the fatigue states presented in section 4. To perform a comparison between controls, a same scenario is proposed for both. During the first seconds, the operation is considered close to the maximum (allowed by wind flow), so the turbines produce a power close to the maximum available power ($P_g^{N_j} \approx P_{av,max}^{N_j}$) and the controller cannot distribute the powers considering the fatigue states of the turbines, since the main objective is to supply the required power. It must be taken into account that the available power varies due to the wake, so that no other possible combination could supply the power required by the central unit. Later, to verify the operation of the control strategy, decrease in demand is produced. To check the veracity of the controllers and facilitate comparison, cluster 1 turbines are analyzed, instead of showing the entire wind farm. All clusters behave in the same way.

5.2.1. Common control strategy based on available power status: Consensus + MPC

Some wind farms still operate with individual control strategies, in which each turbine produces the maximum available, regardless of the behavior of the farm. This behavior is clearly not optimized. To perform a fair comparative, two hierarchical control strategies are presented. Taking into account that common farm control strategies are based on maximizing power through maximizing available power, such as [2, 3], and that consensus or multi-agent algorithms are strategies usually used in this field [7, 16], we present a common wind farm control strategy case in which consensus algorithms distribute the power according to the maximum available power, while an MPC ensures the grid power tracking.

Figure 5: Results for the cluster 1 of the wind farm applying a classic control strategy

Figure 5 presents the results of implementing this strategy. Turbine 1, in blue, is the free-stream turbine, so it is interfaced by the nominal wind speed. The rest of the turbines, due to wake effects, are not interfaced by the same wind speed, so the amount of power available and therefore their maximum power to produce, is reduced.

Finally, power set-points distribution is carried out proportionally to the turbine maximum available power. In this way, the controller dispatches higher power requirements to the first upstream rows of turbines, and lower to the most downstream rows. With this distribution, turbines with a higher fatigue ratio continue to increase their value regardless of their condition. This type of controllers are usually used to maximize the available power and the power reserves of wind farms, but by not taking into account the health of the turbines, the park useful life will be reduced, being exposed to higher maintenance costs.

5.2.2. Proposed control strategy based on fatigue status: Non-Centralized Hierarchical MPC

The obtained results of the proposed strategy are shown in figure 6. In the first graph, dispatch of active powers is shown. The following two graphs show the bending moment and shaft moment ratios, which represent the fatigue status each turbine has, with respect to the rest of the turbines in the cluster. The sum of the ratios of each cluster equals one. Finally, the interfaced wind speed for each turbine is shown, considering wake effects, expressed as available wind. Note, that the available wind is closely related to the available power.

During the first seconds, due to grid requirements, the power generated by each turbine is the maximum allowed by the wind. This causes a distribution of the wake effect, producing a progressive decrease in turbines T_2, T_3, T_4, T_5 and T_6 , as can be seen in the available wind plot. Hence, the turbine with the worst health status, is the free-stream turbine, T_1 , as observed in the second and third subplots,

Figure 6: Results for the implemented hierarchical control, considering turbine fatigue status

Figure 7: Power Reference Tracking

since both bending moment and shaft torque ratios are the highest in the cluster. In a proportional way to the power they deliver, downstream turbines T_2 , T_3 , T_4 , T_5 and T_6 maintain the same order of fatigue, being T_2 more affected than T_3 , and so on.

At 125s, a decrease in the WF power demand is produced, which means new instructions for the controllers. Since the CLC controllers already know the fatigue of the turbines, they begin to adjust the power set-points causing wakes readjustment. Therefore, now the turbines with better fatigue status will be in charge of providing more power to the cluster.

At around 200s, T_1 , the one with the worst fatigue status, starts to produce a lower amount of power, but always within the limit values. The rest of the turbines receive the new power instructions and a greater amount of wind due to the reconfiguration of the wake, always considering the wake delay $\tau_{i,j}$ (10), and they begin to provide more power in the cluster. When turbine T_2 has a high accumulated fatigue ratio, the controller orders it to produce less, and the downstream turbines to increase its power input.

The controller will always be able to readjust the set-points and will ensure that the fatigue conditions of the turbines are not very uneven. Looking around 600s, the first three turbines T_1 , T_2 , T_3 , are providing a minimum power

Figure 8: Results for the implemented hierarchical control, considering turbine fatigue status (section 5.2.2) and Common control strategy based on available power (section 5.2.1). Values expressed in percentage.

and the turbines with better fatigue status, T_5 and T_6 , are beginning to be the wind farm main contributors, also due to the fact that the adjustment wake allows them to have enough wind to do so.

Consequently, this demonstrates the correct operation of an intelligent control that will be internally self-adjusting to equalize the fatigue of the turbines over time, which will mean an increase in the health and useful life of the turbines and therefore also of the wind farm.

5.3. Method comparison analysis

Finally, a brief comparative analysis between the previously implemented controls is performed. Turbine fatigue mean values during the analyzed operating time (700s) are shown in the comparative bar graph of figure 8.

Analyzing the results the increases of the downstream turbines and the decreases of the upstream ones can be observed. The turbines subject to greater fatigue is reduced by 25% and the second most affected, by 11%. These values are subject to analysis time, but clearly justify the effect of the controller.

Conclusions

Life-extension and power maximization of offshore wind farms is of relevance to achieve energy cost reductions. The loads and fatigue of floating wind are more complex than conventional onshore wind turbines due to the additional dynamics and stresses brought by the hydrodynamics.

In order to solve such problems, this article has proposed a control strategy, based on active power dispatching, with the aim of optimizing the distribution of fatigue in floating offshore wind farms. Based on a hierarchical control structure, by adjusting the active power references of wind turbines, the problem of uneven distribution of fatigue in long-term operating offshore wind farms has been solved. By modelling the main loads that cause fatigue in floating wind turbines with a spar base and taking into account the wake

effect, the control has been able to proportionally distribute power references considering the wind farm fatigue states. Cluster controllers redistribute the dispatch power reference instruction, considering the wind farm fatigue states, while fulfilling the demand orders imposed by the central controller.

The obtained results have shown the control effectiveness of self-adjusting the distribution of fatigue by increasing the participation of the downstream wind turbines. Lastly, by comparing the proposed strategy with a power available dispatch based one, it has been obtained that the most affected wind turbine is reduced by 25% and the downstream turbines incremented its participation, achieving a more even fatigue distribution.

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